

Investigation of Curcuminoid Contents from Various Turmeric Plants in Bago Region by Using UV-Visible Spectroscopic Technique

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Abstract

In medicine science, curcuminoid help people as a species, subject food and coloring material. Most of their colorants are extracted from plant materials. Natural colorants are made from renewable resources. It is main yellow bioactive component of turmeric plant. The selected research area is in Bago region. Curcuminoid is the used as a wide spectrum of biological actions. Phytochemical constituents were studied by using different solvents with standard methods. This test revealed that glycoside, carbohydrates, α -amino acid, flavonoids, terpenoid, steroids, saponin, tannin, phenolic compounds, reducing sugar. These samples show that average moisture content (~ 9.05 %). The curcuminoid content is extracted by using Soxhlet and solvent extraction method. The various extract curcuminoid contents were measured by UV-Visible spectrophotometer, UV-2600, Shimadzu, Japan. The contents of curcuminoids were found to be 85.137 mg/L, 86.707 mg/L, 109.001 mg/L in *Curcuma longa* L., from Shwe Kyin, Paya Gyi and Pain Za Loke respectively. From the overall assessments of the research work, 109 mg/L curcuminoid content was interestingly extracted from Pain Za Loke area.

Introduction

Turmeric, i.e., the ground rhizome of *Curcuma longa* L., has a long history of use in food as spices, mainly as an ingredient in many varieties of curry powder and sauces, where curcumin from turmeric plant is a mainly coloring substance. Curcumin is the principal curcuminoids of the turmeric plant. Turmeric and its active component curcumin have received considerable attention due to their many recognized biological activities. *Curcuma longa* L., have been traditionally used in Asian countries as a medicinal herb due to its anti-oxidants, anti-inflammatory, anti-mutagenic, anti-microbial, anti-cancer properties.

Curcuma longa L., which belongs to the Zingiberaceae family, is a perennial herb that measures up to 1 m high with a short stem, distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of the world, being widely cultivated in Asiatic countries, mainly in India and China. *Curcuma longa* L., botanically related to ginger family. Curcumin is the principal curcuminoids of the popular Indian spice turmeric, which is a member of the ginger family (Zingiberaceae). It is grown widely throughout in Myanmar. Curcumin is extracted from dried root of the rhizome *Curcuma longa* L.,. The roots are known to be antiseptic and aromatic. Curcumin is a bright yellow chemical produced by some plants.

Curcuma longa L., is a perennial herb 60-100 cm high with a short stem and tufted leaves. The leaves are in the form elliptic blade in lefts up to 1 m or longer. The stem is as long as the blade, tapering at the base. Flower in autumnal spikes is 10-15 cm long and flowering bracts are pale green. The commercial turmeric consists of primary rhizomes these are ovate, oblong, denominated 'bulb' or round turmeric. The external rhizome is yellowish or yellowish brown. The internal rhizome is yellow or yellow orange. The corolla lobes are pale yellow. Flowering bracts are pale green and bracts of coma tinged with pink. The odors are aromatic and the taste is warm and somewhat bitter. The plant of *Curcuma longa* L., is shown in Figure-1.

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Botanical Description

Myanmar name	:	Na –Nwin
Botanical name	:	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.
English name	:	Turmeric
Family name	:	Zingiberaceae
Chemical name	:	Curcumin
Part use	:	Rhizome

Figure-1(b): Root of *Curcuma longa*

Curcuminoids comprise about 2 – 9 % of *Curcuma longa* L.,. Curcuminoid is a rich source of *Curcuma longa* L.,.Component of turmeric are named Curcuminoids, which included namely curcumin, demethoxycurcumin and bisdemethoxycurcumin. The extract from *Curcuma longa* L., rhizomes has a yellowish brown color and it contain curcuminoids, which also has antioxidant activities with anti-mutagenic effects. This property is responsible for cancer prevention because it can help in the regression of precancer lesions. Curcuminoids content of *Curcuma longa* L., are known to be dependent on the growth and development conditions of rhizome.

Materials and Methods

The rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* L., were collected from Shwe Kyin, Paya Gyi and Pain Za Loke from Bago Regions as shown in Figure-2.

Figure-2: Map of sample collection area in Bago region

The rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* L., stocks are large ovoid with sessile cylindrical tubers orange color insides. Leaves are very large size and in tuft up to 1.2-1.5 m. The petioles are as long as the blades, oblong lance late, tapering to the base. The fresh rhizomes were washed with water to remove impurities and then air dried at shade to prevent some reaction of sunlight with original constituents of the samples. The dried rhizomes were separately cut into piece and ground in a grinding machine. The dried powdered samples were separately stored in the air tight container so that the samples were free from getting molds as well as other continuation and were ready to be used for the experiment work as shown in Figure-3.

Figure-3(a): Rhizome of *Curcuma longa*

Figure-3(b): Powder of *Curcuma longa*

A dried powder sample (25 g) was placed on a Whitman No.1 filter paper. The paper and sample were placed with a flat-free cotton bag and thread. The package of the sample was placed in the central siphon portion of the Soxhlet apparatus. Redistilled ethanol (79 °C) (100 mL) was added into a dried 250 mL round bottom flask, which was connected to a Soxhlet siphon and condenser. The Soxhlet extraction was placed onto a distillation flask containing of 95 % ethanol of extraction solvent and extracted for 18 h. At the end of the extraction process the flask containing the color soluble solvent was obtained together the resin, volatile oils and other extractable plant part.

UV-Visible analysis was carried out by using UV-2600, Shimadzu, Japan, UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The official standard method for determination of *Curcuma longa* L., based products is UV-Vis spectrophotometer which is relied on direct measurements of sample in certain solvents. The UV spectrum is a plot of wavelength of light absorbed versus the absorption intensity and is conveniently recorded by plotting molar absorptivity against wavelength (nm). However, it should be taken into account that the presence of other species having the chromophoric groups absorbing at this wavelength will influence the accuracy of these results. The quantification of curcuminoid using UV-Vis spectrometry technique was usually expressed as the total curcuminoid content. Small amount of curcuminoid was dissolved in ethanol and the solution was placed in curvette. Blank solution was also examined. Measurements were done in the range between 300 nm to 600 nm and the wavelength at maximum absorption was determined (λ_{max}). The solution of curcuminoid ethanol has give characteristics absorption bands in the region between 240 nm and 430 nm with maximum absorption at 429 nm. The European Commission (EC) has specified to use $\lambda_{max} \sim 429$ nm, whereas other regulatory authorities stated λ_{max} between 420 nm and 430 nm.

Results and Discussion

Phytochemical investigations of are qualitative identification tests. The petroleum ether and ethanol extracts were used for phytochemical tests. The results are shown in Table-1. According to these results, it indicated the present of glycoside, carbohydrate, α -amino acid, flavonoid, terpenoid, steroids, phenolic compound, tannin and saponin. However, alkaloids and reducing sugar were absent.

Table-1: Results of Preliminary Phytochemical Investigation of *Curcuma longa* L.,

No	Type of compounds	Extract	Test of reagents	Observation	Remark
1	Alkaloid	1 % HCl	Mayer's reagent	No. ppt	-
			Drangedroff's reagent	No. ppt	-
			Wagner's reagent	No.ppt	-
2	Glycoside	H ₂ O	10 % lead acetate	ppt (white)	+
3	Carbohydrate	H ₂ O	10 % α - naphthol and conc: H ₂ SO ₄	Red ring	+
4	α - amino acid	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin reagent	Pink	+

No	Type of compounds	Extract	Test of reagents	Observation	Remark
5	Flavonoid	70 % EtOH	Mg turning and conc: HCl	Pink color	+
6	Terpenoid and steroids	PE	Acetic anhydride and conc: H ₂ SO ₄	Blue	+
7	Phenolic compound	H ₂ O	Ferric Chloride (5 %)	Blue	+
8	Tannins	H ₂ O	2 % NaCl and 1 % Gelatin	ppt (white)	+
9	Saponin	H ₂ O	Distilled water	Frothing	+
10	Reducing Sugar	H ₂ SO ₄ (dil)	NaOH (dil) and Benedict's solution	No. ppt	-

(+) present, (-) absent, ppt = precipitate

The powder sample was directly placed in oven at 105 °C. The average moisture content of sample was found to be ~ 9 %. The average moisture content of powder samples used in this work is shown in Table-2.

Table-2: Moisture Contents of Curcuminoid

Name of Sample	Parameter	% Content
Shwe Kyin	Moisture	8.10 ± 0.66
Pain Za Loke	Moisture	9.01 ± 0.64
Paya Gyi	Moisture	10.04 ± 0.65
Average moisture content		9.05 ± 0.65

The absorbing peak of sample at 429 nm wavelengths agreed with the standard wavelength of curcuminoid 429 nm Table-3 and Figure-4.

Table-3: Maximum Wavelength of Standard Curcuminoid Compound in 300-600 nm

No	Sample	Wavelength / nm	Absorbance
1	Standard curcuminoid	429.20	1.402

Figure-4: λ_{\max} Spectrum of standard Curcuminoid compound in 300-600 nm

The standard calibration curve of curcuma was obtained by measuring the absorbance of curcumin solution in concentration range (6.25, 12.5, 25 ppm) prepared from stock solutions in ethanol at 429 nm in triplicate. Calibration curve of the curcuminoid was then plotted with absorbance on Y-axis and curcuminoid concentration on X-axis. The absorbing peak of sample at 429 nm wavelengths agreed with the standard wavelength of curcuminoid as shown in Table-4 and Figure-5.

Table-4: Preparation of Standard Calibration Curve

No	Sample	Concentration	Wavelength 429.5
1	Blank	0.000	0.005
2	Standard 1	6.250	0.345
3	Standard 2	12.50	0.697
4	Standard 3	25.00	1.428

Figure-5: Calibration curve for various standard Curcuminoid solution at 429 nm

The determination of how much curcuminoids are present in various local turmeric plants (Shwe Kyin, Paya Gyi and Pain Za Loke) were measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy method at a maximum wavelength of 429.5 nm. The curcumin content is measured at room temperature and pH 10.4. From this research, it was found to be 85, 87 and 109 mg/L from various sites (Shwe Kyin, Paya Gyi and Pain Za Loke). In these samples, turmeric plant from Pain Za Loke area has the highest curcuminoid content. These results are shown in Table-5 and Figure-6 and 7.

Table-5: Curcuminoid Content of Various Samples in Bago Region

Sequence No	Samples	Content mg/L	Absorption (at 429.5 nm)
1	Shwe Kyin	85.137	4.853
2	Paya Gyi	86.707	4.943
3	Pain Za Loke	109.001	6.225

Figure-6: Curcuminoid content of various samples in Bago region

Figure-7: Comparison for Curcumin contents in various samples from Bago region

Conclusion

Rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* L. were collected from Bago region. The dried rhizome powder was extracted with 98 % ethanol. In phytochemical investigations, glycosides, carbohydrates, α - amino acids, flavonoids, terpenoids and steroids, saponins, tannins, phenolic compounds were present. However, alkaloids and reducing sugars were absent. The average moisture content of rhizome samples was found to be 9.05 %. The absorption spectra of curcumin molecule at buffer solution pH of 10.4, were recorded. The wavelength of maximum absorption of curcumin molecule and curcuminoid was found to be 429.5 nm. From the overall assessments of the research work, the following inference would be deduced, 109 mg/L curcuminoid content was extracted from Pain Za Loke area.

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